

doi:10.5281/zenodo.14368379

Administrative Task Performance Of Principals As Correlate Of Teacher Productivity In Public Senior Secondary Schools In Rivers State, Nigeria

¹Okwai, Philip Niebari & ²Prof. K. K. Obasi

**Department of Educational Management,
Faculty of Education,
University of Port Harcourt, Port Harcourt, Nigeria**
¹E-mail: philipokwai@gmail.com/Tel: +2348033879845
²E-mail: padrekenkel@yahoo.com/Tel: +2348033094970

ABSTRACT

This study investigated administrative task performance of principals as correlate of teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The study adopted a correlational design. The population of the study comprised the 311 principals and 6,174 teachers of all the 311 public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The sample of this study comprised all the 311 principals and 679 teachers totaling 990 respondents. Census sampling technique was used to select the principals for the study. Meanwhile, stratify random sampling technique was used to select 679 teachers which is 11% of teachers in all the schools. The instruments for data collection were two sets of questionnaire titled: Administrative Task Performances of Principals Questionnaire (ATPPQ) and Teacher Productivity Questionnaire (TPQ). Cronbach Alpha was used to get an average reliability coefficient of 0.879. The statistics that were used to answer research questions 1-3 was simple regression. The null hypotheses for hypotheses 1-3 were tested using t-test associated regression analysis statistics at 0.05 alpha level. In the findings, 58.2% change in teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State is positively and highly correlated with student personnel administration, while 41.8% was accounted for by other variables not considered in this study. 38% change in teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State is positively and highly correlated with staff personnel administration, while 62% was accounted for by other variables not considered in this study. 64.2% change in teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State is positively and highly correlated with financial management, while 35.8% was accounted for by other variables not considered in this study. The study concluded that there is a significant relationship that exists between administrative task performance of principals in relation to student personnel administration, staff personnel administration and financial management and teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers. It was recommended that: principals should have good managerial skills to plan on how resources will be well utilized to achieve set objectives in schools thereby making the teachers productive.

Keywords: Administrative Task Performances, Teacher Productivity, Student Personnel Administration

INTRODUCTION

The administrative task of a school principal is probably one of the most important aspects of school leadership. The principal performs many administrative tasks for the proper operation of the school. The extent to which the school principal can effectively perform these tasks depends on his leadership qualities. In secondary schools, the principal is the coordinator of the entire secondary school

activities, and maintains a harmonious relationship with the teachers as subordinates and collaborators to ensure the success of school administration. The principal is essentially an organizer and implementer of plans, policies and programmes meant for specific educational objectives. His administrative tasks include among other things: instructional supervision, financial management, student personnel administration, staff personnel administration, school community relations management, curriculum development, instructional leadership as well as school programme planning (Akpagwu, 2012; Omiebi-Davids, 2014).

Indicators of administrative effectiveness of principals as identified by Lunenburg, et al as cited in Odike (2018) include:

- A safe and orderly environment that is not oppressive and is conducive for teaching and learning;
- A clear school mission through which the staff shares a commitment to instructional goals, priorities, assessment procedures and accountability.
- Instructional leadership by school head who understands and applies the characteristics of instructional effectiveness.
- A climate of high expectation in which the staff demonstrates that all students can attain mastery of basic skills.
- High time on task brought about when a high percentage of students' time is spent in planned activities to master basic skills.
- Frequent monitoring of student progress, using the results to improve individual performance and the instructional programme.
- Positive home-school relations in which parents support the school's basic mission and play an important part in trying to achieve it.

On the other hand, productivity is the measure of how well resources are brought together in organizations and utilized for accomplishing a set of results within a specific period of time. Fabunmi as cited in Isere (2017, p. 23) defined productivity as the "output of individuals or group of individuals". Clarifications on the concept revealed that productivity involves notable elements like "inputs, outputs, processes and time respectively. Productivity is the relationship between output of goods and services and inputs of resources, human and non-human, used in the production process. Based on this, productivity in the educational system refers to the ratio between the total educational outputs and the resource inputs utilized in the production process.

A major resource input to the education system is the teaching manpower made up of teachers and principals. Principals are school heads in secondary schools. Teacher productivity on the other hand is seen as a measure of the efficiency with which the overall process of teaching and learning utilizes its labour force (Isere, 2017). Productivity of teachers refers to the degree to which teachers discharge their primary duties of teaching and learning, as well as their general attitude towards the teaching profession and other activities (Owan, 2012). Bolarinwa (2016) stated that, the indicator of teacher productivity is evaluated in the teachers' ability to make a deliberate effort to enhance students' academic performance, possession and display of in-depth knowledge of subject matter, lesson presentation, effective classroom organization and control, and participation in the school curriculum activities.

Student personnel management is one of the essential functions of the school administrator. It is defined as involving all the activities that are rendered to the students for the achievement of educational objectives apart from the normal classroom instructions. Mgbodile as cited in Nzokurum and Ukamaka (2017) further explained that the role of principals in students' personnel administration lies in helping to secure discipline among the students, monitor their attitude to their studies and their commitment to hard work and learning. When principals are able to manage student personnel in school, it will set a good standard for teachers to be productive in teaching and learning activities. Principals have the responsibilities of carrying out disciplinary actions in the school to discipline the students and to make them to be law abiding to ease the work of the teacher so that they can achieve their goals.

Research carried out by Nkwah (2011) revealed that principals through personnel administration were moderately effective in financial and school business administration, students' personnel administration, staff personnel administration, instruction and curriculum development and in general

tasks which helps in the productivity of the entire school system. In the same vein, Owan and Ekaette (2019) revealed that, students' counselling, healthcare, and discipline management are found to be significantly related to students' academic effectiveness in terms of punctuality to classes, time management, study habits, record keeping, attitudes during classes, note taking, attitudes towards assignment, examination results and attitudes towards co-curricular activities.

The study of Nwazue (2021) revealed that the correlation coefficient between students' personnel services such as provision of hostel accommodation, convenience, water, recreational facilities, health facilities, classrooms, and effective administration of school essentially aids the productivity of teachers and students alike. Meanwhile, personnel administration is the various works or efforts put in place by the school principal to bring about the best in the teachers for the organization's growth and development cannot be over emphasized (Akpagwu, 2012). The functional scope of staff personnel administration as stated by Benson (2018), included: determining the personnel needs of the school, (tutorial and non-tutorial), satisfying personnel needs and maintaining and improving services of the staff.

In relation to school, teachers as staff are personnel that the principals of the school need to collaborate very well with so that they can give their best in the teaching and learning responsibilities and also contribute immensely to the general management of the school. In managing staff personnel, Owan and Agunwa (2019) revealed that, principals' supervisory, leadership and communication competences are significantly related to teachers' work performance in terms of instructional delivery, attendance to classes, notes writing, and record keeping respectively. It was also revealed that; principals' supervisory leadership and communication competences have significant composite influence on teachers' work performance in terms of instructional delivery.

The work of Ohia and Odeneke (2018) revealed that, principals' management of teachers through retraining programmes would introduce teachers to new teaching methodologies and technologies that will make them to be more productive in carrying out their responsibility. It was also revealed that, for teachers to be adequately informed and productive, workshops and seminars were given priority in public secondary schools in Bayelsa State. Momoh and Obiweluzor (2015) in their study found that, there was also a significant relationship between administrative effectiveness and implementation of quality assurance standards in the States based on principals' gender and experience which also go in line with the findings of this work. This is in line with Wenzare (2012) which suggested welfare packages like medical allowances, transportation allowances to be given to teachers to enhance their productive performance.

More so, Jideofor (2022) also found that, principals implement personnel management strategies by using advertisement to announce recruitment of personnel, using written interview in the selection of personnel, short listing of the successful candidates, making provision in the work place for personnel safety and carrying out induction exercise for the newly recruited staff as a personnel management strategy for enhancing teacher job performance and boosting their productivity. Notably, some major task areas of personnel management include planning, organizing, directing and controlling which under administrative circumstance should be applied in school administration. The principal as the Chief Executive of the school must make it possible for staff to have access to suitable facilities of all kinds in order to carry out their responsibilities in achieving the educational objectives (Ayeni, 2012). For teaching personnel to be productive in their work, educational institutions can incorporate in their teaching personnel digital skills in ICT to be able to handle and utilize packages like Moodle, Google-Suite (G Suite) for Education, as well as Google's core services, including Gmail, Calendar, Docs, Sheets, Forms, Slides, Hangouts, and more. Additional services include products like Chrome and YouTube, Flipgrid, Facebook, Whatsap, Twitter, Skype, MySpace as well as Yahoo Messenger for communication; sharing of ideas, sharing of photos and videos by users to develop people in these modern times that can work to re-engineer our society for quality existence (International Labour Organization – ILO, 2020).

With regards to teachers' productivity, teachers must be managed on instructional content to have knowledge of some current e-learning resources useable in teaching-learning in a remote setting which include; Web Sites, Online Databases, E-Journals, E-Books, Databases, Cds/Dvds, E-Conference Proceedings, E-Reports, E-Maps, E-Pictures/Photographs, E-Manuscripts, E-Theses, E-Newspaper, Internet/Websites - Listservs, Newsgroups, subject Gateways, USENET and Faqsetc

(Asur & Huberman, 2019). This aspect will help them to be fit in discharging their teaching duties in a more productive manner.

Financial management has a strong relationship with teacher performance in school as it aids the provision of necessary facilities that tend to affect the health, behaviour, engagement, learning, activeness of teachers and growth of the students. The physical and emotional health of students and teachers also depends to a great extent on the facilities provided or available for use in meeting the goals and objectives of the school programme (Kayode & Naicker, 2019). In a situation where principals are not prudent enough to manage such finances, it will definitely affect the productivity of teachers and the performance of students. Mismanagement of finances tends to render school management handicapped in their bid to coordinate and manage the school programmes.

Wenzare (2012) revealed that welfare packages like medical allowances, transportation allowances and other financial allowances given to teachers help in motivating them to be more productive in the job, supported this study. So, when teachers' welfare packages are prioritized, teachers are more committed and their productivity is high. This is why the study of Fadeyi, Sofoluwe, and Gbadeyan (2015) revealed a significant relationship between teacher's salary, promotion and students' academic performance. The work of Titus and Ukaigwe (2019) revealed that effective financial management is needed in institutions by principals of schools to avoid fund mismanagement, and once this is done, it would make room for both human and material resources to be provided at ease that would help the teachers to handle their job in a more productive manner, most especially with necessary supervision.

Statement of the Problem

Teachers are unarguably the most critical professionals in the socio-economic development of a nation because they are at the center of every education system that supplies the relevant manpower for the different sectors of the national economy. Among them are the principals who are saddled with the administrative tasks of the schools. However, a close observation of many public senior secondary schools show a seemingly high level of teacher disloyalty, discouragement, absenteeism, lateness to work and sometimes engage in doing private business at official time, loitering and mismanagement of teaching time. Teachers' productivity seems to be affected by the way they are cared for which eventually affects students' performance in school.

Also, opinions abound on lack of effective communication between teachers and school principals, low teacher productivity that consequently leads to poor academic performance of students. The rate at which staff and students engage in indisciplinary acts is alarming. Could these be as a result of poor administrative task performance of principals? Nevertheless, the fear these could cause led the researchers to examine the relationship that exists between administrative task performance of principals as correlate of teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Purpose of the Study

The study investigated the relationship between the administrative task performances of principals and teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. ascertain the relationship between student personnel administration and teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. determine the relationship between staff personnel administration and teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
3. determine the relationship between financial management and teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

1. What is the relationship between student personnel administration and teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?
2. What is the relationship between staff personnel administration and teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?
3. How does financial management relate to teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between student personnel administration and teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

2. Staff personnel administration does not relate significantly to teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
3. Financial management does not relate significantly to teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

The design for the study was correlational. The population of the study comprised the 311 principals and 6,174 teachers of all the 311 public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, totaling 6,485 respondents. The sample of this study comprised all the 311 principals and 679 teachers totaling 990 respondents in these public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Census sampling technique was used to select the principals for the study. Meanwhile, stratify random sampling technique was used to select 679 teachers which is 11% of teachers in all the schools.

The instruments for data collection were two sets of questionnaire. The first instrument assessed the administrative task performances of principals and it was titled: Administrative Task Performances of Principals Questionnaire (ATPPQ), and the second instrument assesses teacher productivity which was titled: Teacher Productivity Questionnaire (TPQ) designed by the researcher in the modified 4-point Likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA) = 4 points; Agree (A) = 3 points; Disagree (D) = 2 points; and Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1 point. Cronbach Alpha was used to ascertain the reliability coefficients of the instruments. In the reliability result, student personnel administration has 0.916, staff personnel administration has 0.893 and financial management has 0.882. The average reliability stood at 0.879.

The 990 copies of the questionnaire were administered to the respondents by the researcher and five (5) research assistants. The respondents were given at least 2 days to respond to the questionnaire after which the instruments were retrieved by the researcher for data analysis. Only 928 copies were retrieved, giving it 94% retrieval rate. The statistics that were used to answer research questions 1-3 was simple regression. The null hypotheses for hypotheses 1-3 were tested using t-test associated regression analysis statistics at 0.05 alpha level.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question One: *What is the relationship between student personnel administration and teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 1: Simple Regression Analysis on the relationship between student personnel administration and teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	0.763 ^a	0.582	0.581	2.31223	0.582	1286.790	1	926	0.000

Table 1 revealed that the regression coefficient R was calculated to be 0.763 while the regression squared value was computed to be 0.582. This shows that teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State is positively and highly correlated with student personnel administration. Judging by the coefficient of determination, it shows that 58.2% change in teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State is correlated with student personnel administration, while 41.8% was accounted for by other variables not considered in this study.